

PREVALENCE AND ASSOCIATED RISK FACTORS OF TOXOPLASMOSIS AMONG WOMEN IN PARACHINAR DISTRICT KURRAM, KHYBER PAKHTUNKHWA

Sadia Hur^{*1}, Sakina Bibi², Naveed Ullah Khan^{*3}, Ameen Ullah⁴, Abdullah Muslim⁵, Amna khalid⁶, Noor-UL-Eman⁷, Rubab Begum⁸, Shehzad Zareen^{*9}, Muhammad Arsalan¹⁰

^{*1,*3,4,5,6,*9}Department of Zoology, Kohat University of Science and Technology, Kohat, KP, Pakistan

^{2,8}Govt Girls Degree College No 1. Parachinar

⁶Institute of Zoological Sciences, University of Peshawar

¹⁰Department of Zoology, Govt Postgraduate College Karak

¹sadiahir512@gmail.com; ²sakinabibi21303@gmail.com; ³naveed550911@gmail.com; ⁴ameenullahkhan0033@gmail.com; ⁵aliabdullah563@gmail.com; ⁶amna62616@gmail.com; ⁷amiraadakhan05@gmail.com; ⁸rubab1941999@gmail.com; ⁹shehzadzareen1@kust.edu.pk; ¹⁰arsalanktk1919@gmail.com

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17156980>

Keywords

Toxoplasmosis, *Toxoplasma gondii*, Pregnancy, Risk factors, Parachinar

Article History

Received: 21 June 2025

Accepted: 05 September 2025

Published: 19 September 2025

Copyright @Author

Corresponding Authors: *

Sadia Hur

Naveed Ullah Khan

Shehzad Zareen

Abstract

Toxoplasmosis is an infection caused by the protozoan parasite *Toxoplasma gondii*, with cats identified as its definitive host. It is a widespread zoonotic disease and a significant public health concern during pregnancy, associated with miscarriage, premature birth, stillbirth, and fetal abnormalities. This study was conducted to assess the prevalence and risk factors of toxoplasmosis among pregnant women in Parachinar. A total of 460 women were screened, and 105 (23%) tested positive. The highest prevalence was observed in women aged 29–38 years (56.2%), in rural areas (82.9%), among illiterate individuals (35.2%), and housewives (67.6%). Although blood group O (35.2%) and trimester of pregnancy showed higher infection rates, they were not statistically significant. Risk factors included close contact with cats and dogs (73.3%), presence of litter boxes (32.4%), and gardening soil exposure (75.2%). Dietary habits such as consumption of raw vegetables and fruits (77.1%) and beef (47.6%) also increased risk, while raw milk (61%) and uncooked meat (38.1%) were not statistically significant. Use of tap water for drinking (70.5%) showed higher infection rates, though not significant. These findings highlight that environmental exposure, lifestyle, and dietary practices play a major role in the transmission of *T. gondii* among pregnant women. Strengthening awareness and preventive measures is crucial to reduce maternal and fetal complications.

INTRODUCTION

Toxoplasmosis is caused by *Toxoplasma gondii*, a well-known intracellular protozoan parasite. (Yamada et al., 2011). This infection may affect all animals and birds. It's also a major zoonotic infection source (Polley et al., 2009). *T. gondii* is an entirely obligate

protozoan parasite that may cause toxoplasmosis in animals, including humans. Toxoplasmosis is one of the most common infections, affecting one-third of the world's population (Jones et al., 2001). Two microbiologists, Nicolle and Manceaux in 1908 was

initially discovered and separated the *T. gondii* from the blood sample and tissues pieces identified out of a Northern African-based rodent, the *Ctenodactylus gondii* (Nicolle and Manceaux, 1908).

T. gondii is reported to infect various animals and birds, including terrestrial and aquatic mammals and birds. Because of the asexual division in these animals, they are known as intermediate hosts for *T. gondii*. The sexual reproductive phases are best seen in Felidae species, including the domestic cat. Therefore, they are called the definitive host of *T. gondii* (Dubey, 2009). The intermediate hosts can be infected by the following routes which included; ingestion of water, contaminated vegetables, and fruits with possible oocysts sporulated after the previous removal in the faeces of cats, undercooked meat consumption supposedly possessing tissue cysts, congenital transmission from the mother through the placenta, transfusion of blood, organ transplantation, where the organs can also include cysts or tachyzoites. Carnivores (including mammals and birds) or ingestion of sporulated oocysts can infect definitive hosts, such as cats. Oocysts may also remain for a long time in oysters and mussels, keeping their infectious properties (Coupe *et al.*, 2019).

Toxoplasmosis can be transmitted by small ruminant meat, especially in regions where sheep and goat meat are commonly consumed regularly (Garca-Bocanegra *et al.*, 2013; Garcia *et al.*, 2006). Infection can also be spread through milk from affected animals (Boughattas, 2017). Children who suffer from allergies to cow milk, and buffalo milk, prefer to have an intake of small ruminant milk, such as goat milk, in various parts of the world (Latif *et al.*, 2017; Tasawar *et al.*, 2020).

Toxoplasmosis is a disease that can be passed down through the placenta during pregnancy. Although most women with toxoplasmosis have no symptoms (asymptomatic), infection during pregnancy can cause disease transmission through the placenta, resulting in hazardous consequences such as stillbirth, abortion, and exceptional levels of intellectual or physical retardation, blindness, and hydrocephalus (Elsheikha, 2008). The level of congenital transmission of toxoplasmosis as well as its severity in the fetus varies keeping in view the

stages and conditions of pregnancy. Its transmission is lower in the first trimester of pregnancy and keeps on severity to higher levels in the last trimester (Lopes *et al.*, 2012). So the early detection of *T. gondii* infection is mandatory for keeping safe as well as preventing congenital toxoplasmosis. The risk of this congenital infection ranges from 10-25% in the first trimester while during the second trimester it ranges within 30-54% however the range may be higher up to 60-65% in the third and last trimester. On the other hand, even though *T. gondii* infection during embryogenesis is rare, it has a great impact on the fetus. In comparison, asymptomatic newborns are often affected by the maternal disease in the third trimester. If not treated adequately, these babies' retinochoroiditis and neurologic impairments may aggravate in childhood or early adulthood (Assouline *et al.*, 2010).

T. gondii is a parasite that may infect all nucleated cells of a wide range of Worm- blooded animals and causes the most commonly found parasitic zoonosis in the world (Ferreira *et al.*, 2009). Toxoplasmosis has infected more than 6 billion population across the globe. The occurrence of toxoplasmosis in humans differs within and among countries, the previous research indicates the incidence rates of 6.7% in Korea, 12.3% found in China, 23.9% noted in Nigeria, 46.0% pointed out in Tanzania and with the highest range level of 98.0% in some poorly unhygienic segments of other regions (Fromont *et al.*, 2009; Xiao *et al.*, 2010).

Toxoplasma infection rates vary depending on geographic location, dietary patterns, and socioeconomic conditions. The studies conducted on pregnant women for the infection of IgG seropositivity of *T. gondii* was found 44.4% in Izmir, 35.8% noted in Istanbul, 30.7% identified in Ankara, 39.6% quoted in n Malatya, 30.1% conveyed in Aydan, and 19.2% pointed out in Samsun. It was dignified that the *T. gondii* infection is about 42.3% in Black Sea Region, 31-37% in Anatolia, and 69.5% highlighted in Anatolia (Cekin *et al.*, 2011). In Indonesia, toxoplasmosis in livestock is expected to be 51.0% in goats, 8.8% in cattle, and 45.0% in sheep. In some locations of Indonesia, the incidence of human toxoplasmosis has been estimated to range from 43 to 88% (Artama

et al., 2007).

T. gondii is found worldwide and reported in Parachinar city and its surrounding areas. Because of the high illiteracy rate and a lack of information and knowledge about Toxoplasmosis, some patients are turned into very chronic conditions. This virus is spread by eating undercooked or contaminated meat, coming into contact with infected cat faeces, passing it down from mother to fetus during pregnancy, and several other routes. Congenital toxoplasmosis can cause hazardous consequences in children, such as hearing loss, mental disability, and blindness. Keeping in view the existing situation, it was important to recognize the incidence and risk factors that are responsible for the infectious toxoplasmosis in different areas of Parachinar, District Kurram, Khyber Pakhtunkhwa. **Objectives of the study are;**

1: To examine the prevalence of toxoplasmosis among the women of Parachinar.

2: To access the risk factors responsible for causing toxoplasmosis in pregnant women.

STUDY AREA

The study of toxoplasmosis has been conducted in Parachinar, district Kurram, Khyber Pakhtunkhwa (KPK). Parachinar is the district's headquarters and the largest city of district Kurram. The relevant data is collected from both urban and rural areas of Parachinar. Parachinar is situated on a neck of Pakistani territory west of Peshawar and the neighboring provinces of Afghanistan. Parachinar is the nearest point in Pakistan to the Afghan capital Kabul, at 110 kilometers (68 miles).

Figure 1 Map of Parachinar, District Kurram, Khyber Pakhtunkhwa

STUDY DURATION AND DESIGN

I worked to explore the prevalence of *T. gondii* infection in pregnant women of Parachinar from April 2021 to September 2021 and used a questionnaire to achieve research objectives and data represented in the form of tables and graphs. The research aims to find the prevalence and associated risk factors of toxoplasmosis among the women of Parachinar. So, I have selected the questionnaire method as the research tool working for the thesis as it helps to collect possible available information. A structured questionnaire was used to get the data in

an easy way for understanding and statistical treatment. The most common method of generating primary data is through a questionnaire. This method provided more information in a limited time to identify risk factors responsible for transmission.

STUDY CENTERS

The different areas of Parachinar have opted wherefrom data have been collected and visited personally for data collection including;

- The District Head Quarter Hospital Parachinar,
- The Mahmood Hospital Parachinar

- And other maternity centers with Laboratories like;
- Dr. Masooma, Hospital Maternity center,
 - Dr. Rubab Maternity center,
 - Dr. Bahar Hussain, Clinic,
 - Kabir Hussain Clinical Laboratory Parachinar,
 - Raiz Hussain Clinical laboratory Parachinar,
 - Ok Lab opposite to D.H.Q.H Parachinar,
 - Musharaf Hussain New Bangash clinical laboratory in Parachinar,
 - Bangash clinical laboratory and X-Ray near D.H.Q Hospital Parachinar.

DATA COLLECTION

Information and Data were collected from a total of 460 patients. 105 of these patients were identified for toxoplasmosis. The questionnaire was filled out from toxoplasma- positive patients.

QUESTIONNAIRE SURVEY

Under the guidance of a supervisor, a questionnaire was designed to collect and assess the prevalence as well as possible risk factors responsible for toxoplasmosis, which included Patient Name, Age, Residential Area, Education, Profession, Blood Group, Stage of Pregnancy, Source of drinking water, contact with cats and dogs, Litter boxes in-home, cat litter disposing of, Manure Handling, Cattle reared,

contact with Gardening soil, consumption of Meat, Vegetables, Fruits, Milk, Beef, etc. (Annex 1).

DATA ANALYSIS

Data from the questionnaire were fed into Microsoft Excel to build a database. The database was then imported to STATA (V.13) to further statistical analysis. Risk factors assessment was carried out using the Chi-square test, treating negatives as controls. Pearson’s chi-squares (X2) is a statistical approach to assess and categorically treat the data to evaluate the available information on how likely there could be chances for infection. An association was considered significant if the P-value was < 0.05.

RESULTS

This research work is aimed to identify the occurrence and existence as well as associated risk factors of toxoplasmosis among the women of Parachinar. Toxoplasma gondii is a protozoan parasite with a single cell that can infect animals, including humans. This parasite is found throughout the world and reported in Parachinar city and its surrounding areas because of the high illiteracy rate and a lack of information and knowledge about Toxoplasmosis. About 460 patients were interviewed through a questionnaire in different hospitals, laboratories, and healthcare centers in Parachinar. Among them, 105 (23%) patients were identified for toxoplasmosis (Table 1).

Table 1 Prevalence of toxoplasmosis in Parachinar

Toxoplasmosis	Patients	Percentage (%)
Negative	335	(77)
positive	105	(23)
Total	455	(100.00)

The following risk factors which are responsible for toxoplasmosis are;

AGE AS A RISK FACTOR FOR TOXOPLASMOSIS

In this study, the highest percentage of toxoplasmosis is present between the 29 to 38 age group (56.2%). Age is divided into three groups (19-28, 29-38, and 39-48). In the age groups, the prevalence of

toxoplasmosis (is 37.1%) in the age group of 19 to 28, about (56.2%) in the age group of 29 to 38 while (6.7%) in the age group of 39 to 48. However, the result showed that these age groups do not significantly affect acquiring toxoplasmosis (P = 0.436) (Table 2).

Table 2 Age groups in a dataset

Age	Frequency (%)
19-28	39 (37.1)

29-38	59 (56.2)
39-48	7 (6.7)
Total	(100.00)

Pearson chi2 (6) = 5.8867 P = 0.436

AREA AS A RISK FACTOR FOR INFECTION / TOXOPLASMOSIS

The study showed the occurrence and existence of toxoplasmosis in different areas of Parachinar. According to the study, the occurrence of toxoplasmosis is higher in villages / rural areas (82.9%) than in urban. Rural areas are divided into

four groups (north, south, east, and west). The prevalence of toxoplasmosis is (29.5%) in southern areas, (25.7%) in east areas, (22.9%) in western areas, and (4.8%) in northern areas. In Urban (city), the prevalence of toxoplasmosis is (17.1%). However, the result showed that habitat significantly increased the risk of acquiring toxoplasmosis (P = 0.018) (Table 3).

Table 3 Toxoplasmosis in different areas of Parachinar

Residential Area	Frequency (%)
Parachinar City	18 (17.1)
Northern Areas	5 (4.8)
Southern Areas	31 (29.5)
East Areas	27 (25.7)
West Areas	24 (22.9)
Total	(100.00)

Pearson chi2 (12) = 24.3420 P = 0.018

Northern areas of Parachinar: Malana, Luqmankhail

Southern areas of Parachinar: Malikhail, Dall, Shakh, Sidara, Agra, Bisto, Boshehra, Akha Khail, Shablan, Balish Khail, Sultan, Alamsher, Sameer, Ahmad Zai

East areas of Parachinar: Zeran, Kirman, Saragalla, Kachkina

West areas of Parachinar: Shalozan, Tari mangal, Kong Ali zai, Shingak, Borki, Pewar, Nastikot, Noorki, Kharlachi

EDUCATION AS A RISK FACTOR FOR TOXOPLASMOSIS

According to the study, the prevalence of toxoplasmosis is higher in those people who have no education or were illiterate (35.2%), followed by SSC and HSSC (23.8 %), graduate and above (21%), and primary and middle education (20 %). Results showed that illiteracy significantly increased the risk of acquiring toxoplasmosis (P = 0.000) (Table 4).

Table 4 toxoplasmosis among different education levels

Education	Frequency (%)
Illiterate	37 (35.2)
Primary and Middle	21 (20)
SSC and HSSC	25 (23.8)
Graduate and above	22 (21)
Total	(100.00)

Pearson chi2 (6) = 99.2814 P = 0.000

TYPES OF PROFESSION AND TOXOPLASMOSIS

According to the present study, the prevalence of toxoplasmosis was higher in housewives with a percentage of about (67.6%), followed by teachers

(21%), then health workers (11.4%). However, the result showed that types of professions significantly increased the risk of acquiring toxoplasmosis (0.000) (Table 5).

Table 5 toxoplasmosis in a different profession

Profession	Frequency (%)
House wife	71 (67.6)
Teachers	22 (21)
health worker	12 (11.4)
Total	(100.00)

Pearson chi2 (6) = 99.2814 P = 0.000

TYPES OF BLOOD GROUPS AND TOXOPLASMOSIS

According to the present study, the prevalence of toxoplasmosis is the highest percentage in O blood

group patients (35.2%), followed by A group with (33.3%), group with (17.1%), and AB group with (14.3%). However, the result showed that blood group types did not show a significant risk for acquiring toxoplasmosis (P = 0.089) (Table 6).

Table 6 Toxoplasmosis among different blood groups

Blood group	Frequency (%)
o group	37 (35.2)
A group	35 (33.3)
B group	18 (17.1)
AB group	15 (14.3)
Total	(100.00)

STAGES OF PREGNANCY AND TOXOPLASMOSIS

The result revealed that the highest percentage of toxoplasmosis was identified in 1st trimester of the gestation period. The gestation period is divided into three trimesters (1st, 2nd, and 3rd trimester). The

incidence of toxoplasmosis (was 38.1%) in the 1st trimester, (36.2%) in the 3rd trimester, and (25.7%) in the 2nd trimester. However, the result showed that stages of pregnancy did not reflect any remarkable significant association with acquiring toxoplasmosis (P = 0.779) (Table 7).

Table 7 Toxoplasmosis among the different stages of gestation

pregnancy stages	Frequency (%)
1st trimester	40 (38.1)
2nd trimester	27 (25.7)
3rd trimester	38 (36.2)
Total	(100.00)

Pearson chi2 (6) = 3.2335 P = 0.779

SOURCE OF DRINKING WATER AS A RISK FACTOR FOR TOXOPLASMOSIS

According to the study, the incidence of toxoplasmosis is present in the highest percentage (70.5%) in those patients who drink tap water while

(29.5%) present in those patients who drink tube well water. However, the results reflect that the drinking water source does not significantly reduce the risk of acquiring toxoplasmosis (P = 0.326) (Table 8).

Table 8 water source and toxoplasmosis

source of drinking water	Frequency (%)
Tap water	74 (70.5)
Tube well	31 (29.5)
Total	(100.00)

Pearson chi2 (3) = 3.4629 P = 0.326

PRESENCE OF CATS AND DOGS AT HOME AS A RISK FACTOR FOR TOXOPLASMOSIS

The study showed that as the highest range (65.7%) of toxoplasmosis was described in those patients who possessed household cats and dogs while (34.3%) in

those who didn't possess domestic cats and dogs. However, the result presented that the existence of cats and dogs at residential units significantly increased the risk of acquiring toxoplasmosis (P = 0.035) (Table 9).

Table 9 Toxoplasmosis and present of cats and dogs

Presence of dog and cat at home	Frequency (%)
Yes	69 (65.7)
No	36 (34.3)
Total	(100.00)

Pearson chi2 (3) = 8.6285 P = 0.035

CONTACT WITH DOGS AND CATS AS A RISK FACTOR FOR TOXOPLASMOSIS

Most patients (73.3%) claimed that they have direct contact with the cats and dogs, which is the major risk factor for toxoplasmosis because the cat and

dogs are the definitive hosts for the parasite of toxoplasmosis. At the same time, (26.7%) of patients argued that they have no direct contact with dogs and cats. However, the result showed that contact with dogs and cats significantly increased the risk of acquiring toxoplasmosis (P = 0.005) (Table 10).

Table 10 contact with dogs and cats and toxoplasmosis

Contact with dogs and cats	Frequency (%)
Yes	77 (73.3)
No	28 (26.7)
Total	(100.00)

Pearson chi2 (3) = 1.7688 P = 0.005

LITTER BOXES IN A HOME AS A RISK FACTOR FOR TOXOPLASMOSIS

Among the total patients, the majority (67.6%) claimed that they did not have any litter boxes for the cats in their houses, while (32.4%) argued that they

have litter boxes in their places. However, the result showed that the presence of cat litter boxes in the home significantly increased the risk of acquiring toxoplasmosis (P = 0.039) (Table 11).

Table 11 presence of litter boxes and toxoplasmosis

litter Boxes	Frequency (%)
Yes	34 (32.4)
No	71 (67.6)
total	(100.00)

Pearson chi2 (3) = 8.3724 P = 0.039

RESPONSIBILITY OF DISPOSING OF CAT LITTER AS A RISK FACTOR FOR TOXOPLASMOSIS

About (42.9%) of patients claimed that they have the responsibility of disposing of the cat litter, while the

remaining (57.1%) of respondents claimed they did not have any such responsibility. However, the results reflect that statistically, the responsibility of disposing of cat litter does not show any significant risk of acquiring toxoplasmosis (P = 0.133) (Table 12).

Table 12 cat litter responsibility and toxoplasmosis

cat litter responsibility	Frequency (%)
Yes	45 (42.9)
No	60 (57.1)
Total	(100.00)

Pearson chi2 (3) = 5.6002 P = 0.133

MANURE HANDLING AS A RISK FACTOR FOR TOXOPLASMOSIS

The majority of the patients (61%) argued that they have the responsibility for manure handling, while

39.1% said they didn't handle the manure. However, the results reflect that statistically, manure handling does not show any significant risk for acquiring toxoplasmosis (P = 0.503) (Table 13).

Table 13 handling of manure and toxoplasmosis

Manure handling	Frequency (%)
yes	64 (61)
No	41 (39.1)
Total	(100.00)

Pearson chi2 (3) = 2.3517 P = 0.503

CATTLE REARING AS A RISK FACTOR FOR TOXOPLASMOSIS

In the present study, about (39.1%) of patients declared that they rearing the cattle; the remaining

claimed that they did not domesticate the cattle. However, the result showed that the cattle rearing did not display any remarkable significant association with acquiring toxoplasmosis (P = 0.523) (Table 14).

Table 14 cattle rearing and toxoplasmosis

Cattle reared	Frequency (%)
Yes	41 (39.1)
No	64 (61)
Total	(100.00)

Pearson chi2 (3) = 2.2470 P = 0.523

CONTACT WITH GARDENING SOIL AS A RISK FACTOR FOR TOXOPLASMOSIS

About (75.2%) of positive patients with toxoplasmosis have direct contact with the gardening soil. The remaining (24.8%) claimed that they had

not had any contact with the gardening soil. However, the result showed that contact with gardening soil significantly increased the risk of acquiring toxoplasmosis (P = 0.014) (Table 15).

Table 15 contact with gardening soil and toxoplasmosis

Gardening soil	Frequency (%)
yes	79 (75.2)
No	26 (24.8)
Total	(100.00)

Pearson chi2(3) = 6.4627 P = 0.014

Figure 2 Prevalence of Risk Factors Associated with *Toxoplasma gondii* Infection among Pregnant Women in Parachinar

CONSUMPTION OF UNCOOKED/RAW MEAT AS A RISK FACTOR FOR TOXOPLASMOSIS

In the present study, the highest percentage (38.1%) of toxoplasmosis was identified in those patients who consumed meat on a weekly basis while (34.3%) on a

quarterly basis, and the remaining (27.6%) patients consumed meat every month. However, the result displayed that uncooked/raw meat consumption did not show any significant association to acquiring toxoplasmosis (P = 0.689) (Table 16).

Table 16 consumption of meat and toxoplasmosis

consumption of meat	Frequency (%)
weekly	40 (38.1)
Quarterly	36 (34.3)
Monthly	29 (27.6)
Total	105 (100.00)

Pearson chi2 (6) = 3.9095 P = 0.689

CONSUMPTION OF RAW VEGETABLES AND FRUITS AS A RISK FACTOR FOR TOXOPLASMOSIS

The study showed that a high incidence (77.1%) of toxoplasmosis was described in those patients who digest vegetables and fruits on a weekly basis, while (16.2%) was described in those patients who digest

vegetables and fruits on a quarterly basis and remaining (6.7%) in those who digest vegetables and fruits on monthly basis. However, the result disclosed consumption of fruits and vegetables did not show any significant risk of acquiring toxoplasmosis (P = 0.094) (Table 17).

Table 17 consumption of vegetables and Fruits and toxoplasmosis

consumption of vegetables and fruits	Frequency (%)
weekly	81 (77.1)
quarterly	17 (16.2)
Monthly	7 (6.7)
Total	105 (100.00)

Pearson chi2 (6) = 10.8276 P = 0.094

MILK CONSUMPTIONS RISK FACTOR FOR TOXOPLASMOSIS

In the study, most of the patients (61%) claimed that they used milk on a weekly basis, while (21.9%)

argued that they used milk on a quarterly basis and the remaining (17.1%) used it on a monthly basis. However, the result showed that the milk consumption did not show any significant risk for acquiring toxoplasmosis (P = 0.555) (Table 18).

Table 18 Milk consumption and toxoplasmosis

Milk consumption	Frequency (%)
weekly	64 (60.95)
Quarterly	23 (21.90)
Monthly	18 (17.14)
Total	105 (100.00)

Pearson chi2 (6) = 4.9158 P = 0.555

BEEF CONSUMPTION RISK FACTOR FOR TOXOPLASMOSIS

In this study, about (47.6%) of patients claimed that they digest beef on a weekly basis, (41%) of patients argued that they digest beef on a quarterly basis, while

the remaining (11.4%) of patients consumed beef on a monthly basis. Results suggested that the habit of frequent consumption of beef significantly increased the risk of acquiring toxoplasmosis (P = 0.018) (Table 19).

Table 19 consumption of beef and toxoplasmosis

Beef consumption	Frequency (%)
weekly	50 (47.6)
quarterly	43 (41)
monthly	12 (11.4)
Total	105 (100.00)

Table 20. Frequency of Dietary Consumption and Associated Risk Factors for *Toxoplasma gondii* Infection among Pregnant Women in Parachinar

Details	Consumption of Meat	Consumption of Vegetables and Fruits	Milk Consumption	Beef Consumption

Weekly	38%	77%	61%	48%
Quarterly	34%	16%	22%	41%
Monthly	28%	7%	17%	11%

DISCUSSION

This study aimed at investigating *T. gondii* infection in pregnant women and its possible risk factors. The population was selected at my hometown Parachinar. To evaluate the prevalence of *T. gondii* infection among pregnant females, the relevant data is collected from both urban and rural areas of Parachinar through a Questionnaire survey. Because of its complicated nature and transmission, *T. gondii* infection possess a major human hazard. The prevalence of *T. gondii* disease in pregnant females and control subjects has been found at 23%, respectively.

According to epidemiological reports, *T. gondii* infection in females of childbearing age differ greatly between countries. In Europe, *T. gondii* infections highlighted in the pregnant female range from 9% to 67% (Meerburg and Kijlstra, 2009). In contrast, in Asian countries, however, Korean and Vietnamese research studies indicated a low frequency of *T. gondii* infection that is 0.8% and 11.2%, respectively. In comparison, the occurrence of *T.gondii* in pregnant females has been recorded as high as 41.8-55.4% in Indian, Malaysian, and Nepalese populations (Song *et al.*, 2005; Buchy *et al.*, 2003; Rai *et al.*, 1998). The previous report in Ghana found the Occurrence rates of 67.9% and 82.1% in pregnant females aged 15-25 and 31-40 years, respectively (Anteson *et al.*, 1978). In contrast, our study showed that the incidence of *T.gondii* infection is (56.2%) the age range of 29 to 38 years age group but not statistically significant (P = 0.436). The percentage of our result indicates that this age group represented the most active age group among adults (marriage age and childbearing age).

According to some studies, toxoplasmosis is more common in temperate climates and less common in cold, hot, and dry climates. Unsuitable environmental conditions for oocyte development and growth in hot and dry climates could explain the low occurrence of toxoplasmosis in these areas (Mousavi *et al.*, 2012; Fallah *et al.*, 2008). According to (Mahmoudvand *et al.*, 2015) study, the occurrence

of *T. gondii* infection is a significant risk factor for both people who are living in rural and urban areas, which is similar to our study because our result showed that the prevalence of *T. gondii* positivity was higher in those participants whose living in villages and rural areas (82.9%) than those whose living in cities (17.1%). These findings revealed that those people are living in rural areas or farming had a higher possibility of exposure to *T. gondii* because people who are associated with gardening and farming are more likely to become infected. So, our study suggested that habitat is a significant risk factor for acquiring toxoplasmosis (P =0.018).

Keeping in view the possible factor, i.e., education, because the initial prevention of toxoplasmosis pursues to strengthen pregnant females' knowledge and possible information of the causing agents, factors, and routes of transmission. The study has established that illiteracy significantly increased the risk for toxoplasmosis (P = 0.000) because in the present study most pregnant women were illiterate or unaware of toxoplasmosis (35.2%). In previous investigations, common toxoplasmosis knowledge was observed nationwide. Only 9.9% in Egypt had a decent understanding of toxoplasmosis, according to a study by (Abdalla *et al.*, 2014). Similar findings were found in Ethiopia and Tanzania showing that 5% and 5.7% of pregnant females, respectively, were aware of this infection (Onduru *et al.*, 2019; Hdush, 2015). Toxoplasmosis awareness was particularly poor (11%) in Asian countries, i.e. Malaysia, the Philippines, and Thailand (Andiappan *et al.*, 2014). However, our result demonstrated that (67.6%) of positive patients are housewives. Furthermore, the present results contradict the profession and also seem significant risk factors for toxoplasmosis unawareness (P = 0.000). Not knowing about the disease has put pregnant women unaware of toxoplasmosis at a higher risk of infection. They are more likely to contract

T. gondii infection when pregnant, resulting in severe infection and increasing the risks of getting

congenital transmission. So, an equipped knowledge and thorough understanding of toxoplasmosis's transmission routes is critical for preventing infection during pregnancy.

According to the study (Borna *et al.*, 2013) Iranian review, the occurrence of hereditary contagion in the days of pregnancy was projected to be 1–8 per 1000 pregnancies. Hereditary-based toxoplasmosis is the most common fatal infection and a significant risk agent for brain damage and mental retardation in the young fetus. *T. gondii* infection can bring abortion and even stillbirth during the initial months of pregnancy. Our finding demonstrated that about (38.1%) of Toxoplasma infections were identified in 1st trimester of the gestation period, which did not show any significant association with acquiring toxoplasmosis ($P = 0.779$). Hence it can be concluded that adequate

treatment for acute infection is extremely required during pregnancy to keep the patient recovered and safe.

T. gondii infection can also be spread by contaminated drinking water (Bowie *et al.*, 1997). *T. gondii* oocysts have been found in wells located on farms (Sroka *et al.*, 2006) and can live in soil and water for long periods (Torrey and Yolken, 2013). According to a study conducted in Nigeria (Ishaku *et al.*, 2009), pregnant women who drank pipe water had a greater prevalence rate than packaged water. Our study found an increased risk of *T. gondii* positivity among participants who used tap water sources for drinking purposes (70.5%) than tube well water (29.5%) but statistically, the result reflected that the drinking water and its source do not have a significant association to acquiring toxoplasmosis ($P = 0.326$). This finding revealed that *T. gondii* contamination of drinking water is prevalent and that drinking boiling water is a good approach to avoid

T. gondii infection.

The definitive host of *T. gondii* are cats, the oocysts are regularly spread through infected cat faeces, serving as a significant source of infection for *T. gondii* in humans (Dubey, 2010). According to previous findings, *T. gondii* is thought to be present in 30–40% of domestic cats globally (Dubey and Beattie, 2010; Webster and Dubey, 2010). However,

more people are keeping pets, such as cats and dogs, which may increase the risk of zoonotic diseases like Toxoplasmosis. Our finding, estimated about (65.7%) of positive patients who possessed domestic cats and dogs, which significantly increased the risk of acquiring toxoplasmosis ($P = 0.035$). Previous epidemiologic research has consistently shown that contact with cats is a risk factor (Cong *et al.*, 2015; Zemene *et al.*, 2012; Rodrigues *et al.*, 2015; Chiang *et al.*, 2012; Agmas *et al.*, 2015). According to our questionnaire survey, (73.3%) of toxoplasma positive patients directly contact cats. However, contact with cat faeces due to owning a cat and/or availability of cats in the immediate surrounding area has been linked to a significantly increased risk of Toxoplasma infection ($P = 0.005$). Because Toxoplasma antibodies were found in higher quantity in pregnant females who had domestic cats at home than in pregnant women who did not have domestic cats, it's possible that the majority of the infected / carrier cats excreting oocyst,

According to (Angulo *et al.*, 1995), the hygiene of litter boxes is the most important precaution to prevent the transmission of toxoplasmosis from pet cats. Our result

revealed that the presence of litter boxes in the home significantly increased the risk for toxoplasmosis ($P = 0.039$); about (32.4%) of positive participants in our study argued that they have cat litter boxes in their home. Our analysis also finds (42.9%) positive patients who are responsible for the removal of cat faeces or cleaning litter boxes, but statistically, the responsibility of disposing of cat litter doesn't show any significant risk for acquiring toxoplasmosis ($P = 0.133$). The litter box found within the environment is expectedly contaminated by infected cats that shed the parasite through faeces. The infected cat can easily contaminate the soil and water in the surrounding. It is suggested to clean the Litter boxes regularly and keep the kitchen as well as dining areas neat and clean.

The inexistence of manure dandling and cattle rearing is also a risk factor for *T. gondii* positivity. Our study investigated that (61%) of positive patients were responsible for manure handling, and (39.1%) of patients declared that they reared the cattle. But the present survey did not suggest that the manure handling ($P = 0.503$) and cattle reared ($P = 0.523$) are

significant factors in disease transmission. According to (Tzanidakis *et al.*, 2012), the availability of manure can be a possible risk factor for *T. gondii*. It can also be expected with a high ratio in grazing areas and the humidity they provide may help oocysts survive in the soil. In indoor and outdoor husbandry systems, *T. gondii* prevalence has been linked to higher animal density.

Other studies (Liu *et al.*, 2009; Fromont *et al.*, 2009, Baril *et al.*, 1999) have shown another risk factor for rural areas with more soil exposure for pregnant females. The Oocysts can survive for years in some environments (Torrey and Yolken, 2013). Our study finds contact with gardening soil significantly increased the risk for disease transmission ($P = 0.014$) with an incidence of (75.2%). Therefore, all soil and sand should be regarded as potential sources of human infection. This factor increases the chance of *T. gondii* disease and possible infection in pregnant females, especially in those living in rural villages and suburban areas of the country. Hence women with more contact with soil get easily infected as compared to those who have fewer contacts.

All of the evidence shows that the oral route is the most common mode of infection involving food preparation and consumption, with raw meat accounting for 30 to 63% of all infections (Cook *et al.*, 2000). The main risk factor for Toxoplasma infection

consistently identified in all centers is undercooked or raw meat (Dubey, 2004). Meat consumption was also responsible for 30 to 63% of diseases in different European locations (Cook *et al.*, 2000). Our study demonstrated a risk of toxoplasmosis (38.1%) in positive patients who consumed Raw/undercooked meat but not statistically significant ($P = 0.689$). About (47.6%) of patients argued that they consumed beef every week. However, the consumption of beef is a significant risk factor for infection of toxoplasmosis in the study ($P = 0.018$). According to (Lass *et al.*, 2012). *T. gondii* oocysts were found in leafy greens, *T. gondii* infection can be spread by eating contaminated, unwashed vegetables and fruits or washing with contaminated water. Our finding also investigated the eating of raw vegetables and fruits with a percentage of (77.1%), but they did not show any significance in our study

($P = 0.094$). However, it can be a factor for preventive measures and an awareness campaign if health issues are addressed to patients.

According to (Robert-Gangneux and Dardé, 2012), unpasteurized milk or milk products were responsible for 14% of infections in Lausanne, but just 5% or below elsewhere. In European countries, a considerable number of infections (14% to 49%) have remained unexplored and unexplained. Our study described that (61%) of total patients consume untreated/unboiled milk, but statistically, the result did not suggest milk consumption as a significantly remarkable risk factor for getting toxoplasmosis ($P = 0.555$). *T. gondii* has been isolated from the unpasteurized milk received from goats, sheep, and cows. Therefore taking and using unpasteurized milk can lead to getting infected with toxoplasmosis.

RECOMMENDATIONS

Based on conclusions from the present study following recommendations for prevention can be formulated;

- Food must be properly cooked at prescribed temperatures to prevent toxoplasmosis and other foodborne infections. To assure that cooked meat is properly through all the way, use a food thermometer to check the internal temperature. Roasts and steaks should be cooked at 145 F and pork, ground meat, at 160 F Poultry at 180 F before consuming.
- Vegetables and fruits should be washed thoroughly before consumption.
- Hands should be cleaned with hot water and soap soon after contacting raw meat, vegetables, poultry, fruits, seafood, and kitchen accessories.
- As cat faces may be present in soil or sand, pregnant females should wear proper gloves if she wants to do gardening. Hands should be properly washed after gardening.
- Pregnant females should not do changing cat litter in their residences. In necessity, gloves must be used and then hands must be washed properly. Because Toxoplasma oocysts take many days to become infectious is recommended that pregnant women keep their cats indoors and not adopt or handle stray cats. Raw or undercooked meats should not be served to cats. Canned and dried food must be

served in such cases.

- Information regarding precautionary measures against toxoplasmosis must be included in health education. Healthcare experts should aware pregnant females about food cleanliness and avoid being exposed to cat faces.
- Using boiled water and pasteurized Malik.
- The government and the meat industry should reduce toxoplasma in meat.
- Implementation of specialized health care programs. Such programs should be needed by the local community to reduce vertical toxoplasmosis transmission.
- There should be pre-natal and post-natal screening for early detection of infection.
- A proper screening test should be advised for all those with a family history of toxoplasmosis.
- Vaccination programs should be launched free of cost by the health authorities

References

- Polley, L.; Thompson, R.C.A. (2009). Parasite zoonoses and climate change: Molecular tools for tracking shifting boundaries. *Trends Parasitol.*, 25, 285-291.
- Jones, J. L., Kruszon-Moran, D., Wilson, M., McQuillan, G., Navin, T., & McAuley, J. B. (2001). Toxoplasma gondii infection in the United States: seroprevalence and risk factors. *American Journal of Epidemiology*, 154(4), 357-365.
- Nicolle, C., & Manceaux, L. (1908). Sur une infection à corps de Leishman (ou organismes voisins) du gondi. *C R Acad Sci (Paris)*, 147, 763-766.
- Dubey, J. P. (2009). History of the discovery of the life cycle of Toxoplasma gondii. *International Journal for Parasitology*, 39(8), 877-882.
- Coupe, A., Howe, L., & Shapiro, K., Roe, W. D. (2019). Comparison of PCR assays to detect Toxoplasma gondii oocysts in green-lipped mussels (*Perna canaliculus*). *Parasitol Res*, 118, 2389-2398.
- García-Bocanegra, I., Cabezón, O., Hernández, E., Martínez-Cruz, M. S., Martínez-Moreno, Á., & Martínez-Moreno, J. (2013). Toxoplasma gondii in ruminant species (cattle, sheep, and goats) from southern Spain. *Revista de Ciencias Veterinarias*, 99, 438-440.
- Garcia, J. L., Navarro, I. T., Vidotto, O., et al. (2006). Toxoplasma gondii: comparison of a rhoptry-ELISA with IFAT and MAT for antibody detection in sera of experimentally infected pigs. 113, 100-105.
- Latif, A. A., Mushtaq, S., Fazal, S., Mansha, M., & Yaqub, A. J. B. (2017). Seroprevalence of Toxoplasma gondii pregnant women in Lahore, Pakistan. *Biologia*, 63(2), 141-146.
- Lopes, A. P., Dubey, J. P., Moutinho, O., et al. (2012). Seroepidemiology of Toxoplasma gondii infection in women from the North of Portugal in their childbearing years. *Epidemiology and Infection*, 140(5), 872-877.
- Assouline, C., Bessières, M. H., Lathière, M., Cassaing, S., Minville, V., et al. (2010). Long-term outcome of children with congenital toxoplasmosis. *Am J Obstet Gynecol*, 203(6), 552.e1-6.
- Ferreira, M. U., Hiramoto, R. M., Aureliano, D. P., da Silva-Nunes, M., da Silva, N. S., Malafronte, R. S., & Muniz, P. T. (2009). A community-based survey of human toxoplasmosis in rural Amazonia: seroprevalence, seroconversion rate and associated risk factors. *Am J Trop Med Hyg*, 81(1), 171-176.
- Fromont, E. G., Riche, B., & Rabilloud, M. (2009). Toxoplasma seroprevalence in a rural population in France: detection of a household effect. *BMC Infectious Diseases*, 9, 76.
- Çekin, Y., Kızılateş, F., Gür, N., & Şenol, Y. (2011). Investigation of Toxoplasma gondii seropositivity in pregnant women attending the Antalya Training and Research Hospital for the last four years. *Türkiye Parazitol Derg*, 35, 181-184.

- Meerburg, B. G., & Kijlstra, A. (2009). Changing climate-changing pathogens: *Toxoplasma gondii* in North-Western Europe. *Parasitol Res*, 105, 17-24.
- Song, K.-J., Shin, J.-C., Shin, H.-J., & Nam, H.-W. (2005). Seroprevalence of toxoplasmosis in Korean pregnant women. *Korean J Parasitol*, 43(2), 69-71.
- Buchy, P., Follezu, J. Y., Lien, T. X., An, T. T., Tram, L. T., Tri, D. V., et al. (2003). Serological study of toxoplasmosis in Vietnam in a population of drug users (Ho Chi Minh city) and pregnant women (NhaTrang). *Bull Soc Pathol Exot*, 96, 46-47.
- Rai, S. K., Shibata, H., Sumi, K., Rai, G., Rai, N., Manandhar, R., et al. (1998). *Toxoplasma* antibody prevalence in Nepalese pregnant women.
- Anteson, R. K., Sekimoto, S., Furukawa, S., Takao, Y., & Nyanotor, M. A. (1978). Studies on toxoplasmosis in Ghana I. The prevalence of toxoplasmosis as measured by the haemagglutination (Eiken) test. *Ghana Med J*, 17, 147-149.
- Mousavi, M., Jamshidi, A., & Reisi, J. M. (2012). Serological study of toxoplasmosis among pregnant women of Nikshahr. *Razi J Med Sci*, 21(123), 45-53.
- Fallah, M., Rabiee, S., Matini, M., & Taherkhani, H. (2008). Seroepidemiology of toxoplasmosis in primigravida women in Hamadan, Islamic Republic of Iran. *East Mediterr Health J*, 14(1), 163-171.
- Mahmoudvand, H., Saedi Dezaki, E., Soleimani, S., Baneshi, M. R., Kheirandish, F., Ezatpour, B., & Zia-Ali, N. (2015). *Parasite Immunol*, 37(7), 362-367.
- Abdalla, S. A. G. M., & Abo Elghite Elhossiny, E. E. (2014). Knowledge and attitude of women regarding toxoplasmosis during pregnancy and measures to overcome it in slum areas. *Int J Curr Res*, 6(4), 6365-6371.
- Onduru, O. G., Rumisha, S. F., Munyeme, M., & Phiri, A. M. (2019). *Afr Health Sci*, 19(4), 3027-3037.
- Gashout, A., Alsaad, R., Al-Kafaji, G., & Sheta, M. (2015). Prevalence of *Toxoplasma gondii* infection in pregnant women in Tripoli, Libya. *Libyan J Med*, 10, 28308.